

Administration Management of Human Resources in Secondary Education an Exploratory Study in Greece

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ABSTRACT: *This study examines the importance of the administration and management of human resources in an organization and more specifically the HRM at school unit, in secondary education. This study consists of two parts. The first part includes the theoretical framework and a literature review of the administration and management of human resources. More specifically, this article addresses the concept, content, and functions of the Administration of a school as well as the concept, content, functions, and the strategic importance of HRM. The importance of this research is significant because administration as well as human resource management in public school institutions is an essential matter. The research methodology and framework used are described in the research section. The opinions of secondary school teachers are explored, regarding how they are trained, how they are treated in their work, how they are evaluated. The results of their numerical and qualitative analysis are summarized below. The final step is to communicate the findings of the research.*

KEYWORDS -Educational administration, Human resources management, Secondary education, School unit

I. INTRODUCTION

With globalization, new conditions were formed in areas such as work (e.g. the need for employees to acquire new skills, the variability of professional life, etc.), economy, society and especially education, and as a result, strengthening the importance of the quality of education internationally. The issue of quality education is at the center of attention of all international organizations dealing with educational issues. The purpose of all this is to upgrade the overall quality of the provided education. There is no unanimity as to which are the special characteristics that the school unit must have in order to be characterized as total quality. Some consider it to be about the completeness of the content of studies, the modernization and suitability of detailed analytical programs and teaching materials, while others consider the way students are assessed, the teaching process, and their performance. Still others attach importance to issues of qualitative and quantitative adequacy of teaching and other staff, while others to the administration and operation of the school unit, to the school climate, in employee relations, to infrastructure issues, to resources, and to fair treatment or to all above.

The central theme of this research concerns the administration and management of human resources in schools, especially in secondary schools and tries to analyze and highlight the importance of this function, considering teachers as the most important resource, who provide the knowledge, skills and energy, which are essential ingredients for the total quality of the education. With the importance of information and communication technology, what differentiates effective and less effective organizations is the quality of provided education and commitment of the people who work there. In countries where basic resources are limited, opportunities for effective education may depend even more on people's attitudes and commitment to them. The goal of HRM, which has been transformed from simple personnel management to strategic human resource management, is to create all the necessary conditions for individuals, especially trainers, to perform at their best. Using these ideas, the current research attempts to understand the current situation in secondary

education, to review the established management of this level of education, as well as to suggest ways to enhance the quality of teaching and learning in public school institutions through the effectiveness of the teachers.

In particular, the work is called upon to investigate the following: – What are the policies and techniques of a modern administration and management of human resources that could be applied in the school units, to produce the abilities and attitudes of the teachers that the school needs, to achieve its strategic objectives, which will maximize the benefits and minimize the negative elements and utilize the most valuable resource? How can the degree of satisfaction derived from the work of the educational staff whose skills and motivations are critical for succeeding the goals of school units at the Greek education system be increased?

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Conceptual clarifications of the management of an organization.

Administration or otherwise management has been the subject of discussions and debates by many scientists resulting in the existence of many different definitions. A common component of all definitions is considered to be the completion of objectives, where it is the cornerstone of any form of administration. An organization or a business, if it does not achieve its goals, ceases to exist. Some define management as the accomplishment of predetermined purposes accomplished by appropriate functions and necessary actions. Drucker (1974[1]) considers that management is the completion of things through human and material resources so that by utilizing different resources management achieves its goals. Hersey & Blanchard (1977[2]) describe it as work where realization is done with individuals and through them and groups the goals of an organization are fulfilled. Pavlopoulos (1983[3]) argues that when the realization of a defined purpose is done in a rational way and with the use of modern planning methods then this constitutes the heart of management. A more recent term of administration refers to management as the completion of the organization's goals, for the successful completion of which you must work together and through other people (Tzortzakis, 1999[4]).

This term focuses on the importance of the human being within the organization it gives maximum importance to the achievement of the result of the purposes and less to the activities introducing the idea of the integration of the purposes of the members with the purposes of the organization. In terms of these definitions the aim is to achieve as many of the co-created objectives as possible. So what we call the managerial phenomenon is the result of the co-creation and harmonization of personal goals with the goals of the organization which are of vital importance to the members of the organization. In order to achieve any goal, each executive acts appropriately. Through the appropriate activity he must harmonize, coordinate and guide the respective resources that will be needed and indeed the most valuable man. Management as a process includes some functions. Functions are considered indivisible, but the science of organization and management tries to separate them into parts such as planning, organizing, directing, coordinating and controlling. These activities as part of management are completely interdependent and help in the efficient use of generally limited resources such as available cash, human, equipment, materials, techniques, processes and information flows.

2.2. Definition and concept of educational unit administration

The importance of education in society is undeniable. According to Xochelis (2004[5]), education refers to the organized and methodical process of education and learning on the part of the state or another official body. Management in school education refers to the way in which the assets and resources of a school are structured, mobilized and coordinated to achieve common goals in a specific time frame and with the best possible result (Theofanidis, 1989[6]), (Drucker et al., 2009[7]). Educational administration is described as the process of coordinating and harmonizing the operations of a school in order to achieve the specific goals of the school as well as its members as effectively as possible. According to Bush (1999[8]) teacher management is described as "the synchronization of many aspects".

Educational administration is approached as a social process. The educational unit as an open social system is defined by a variety of relationships, modes of connection and interdependencies. As an open system of inputs and outputs where resources and initial behaviors are transformed through educational processes into

goods and services that have a direct impact on civil society (research, innovation and citizen satisfaction) as recipients of educational value. As a result the external environment, the local community and the local government are all intertwined with the dynamic interaction of the educational unit with the community, the cooperation of the local government with the functioning of collective bodies and the participation in social events, ideas and actions those who have an important role in developing this link, such as school principals and members of local education boards. Managerial practices are a collection of specialized operational activities, such as planning, organizational decision-making, management, and control, which are used to achieve predetermined goals within an organization. Both the organizational and the ideological or human dimension of a social system are important. The field of education is seen as a series of open systems that are affected by their environment from the systemic, holistic perspective. Open systems centered on people and material resources are what are classified in educational institutions (Katsaros, 2008[9]). As the industry's open systems evolve, so does the faculty composition. This is demonstrated by the fact that there is no single approach to the organization and management of teachers (Hatzipanagiotou, 2003[10]).

Defining effectiveness in education is not easy because there is a relative inability to define purpose and goals (Bush, 2002[11]). Bolam (1999[12]) defines education administration as "an executive function to implement agreed policy". He differentiates administration from educational leadership which has "at its core the responsibility for policy formulation and where appropriate, organizational transformation". Bush (2003[13]) argues that educational management should be primarily concerned with the purpose or goals of education. These goals or objectives provide the critical sense of direction that should underpin the management of educational institutions. Management aims to achieve specific educational goals. Unless this link between purpose and management is clear and close, there is a risk of 'managerialism', and an 'emphasis on procedures at the expense of educational purpose and values' (Bush 1999[14]).

2.3. The administration and governance of school education

The administration and governance of school education is developed:

At a central level by the Ministry of Education and Religious Affairs.

At the regional level from the regional directorates of primary and secondary education.

At prefectural level from the directorates of primary and secondary education.

At the level of educational units.

2.4. Governing bodies of school units

The governing bodies of the school units, which are responsible for their daily operation, are:

I) administrative (principal of the school unit, the vice-principal and the teachers' association), II) external administrative (school committee), III) supportive (school counselor, parents' association). According to Greek secondary education legislation, the head of the school unit is responsible for overseeing the day-to-day operations of the school, as well as coordinating activities, enforcing compliance with relevant legislation and official orders, and implementing any actions of the teachers' union. It also participates in teacher performance evaluation and works closely with school associations. It is also important to note that the primary role of the vice-principal is to serve as an interim authority in the absence/incapacity of the school principal, with primary responsibility for managing the current needs of the school. Last but not least the teaching union, which includes all the teaching staff, acts as a collegial body to set guidelines and improve the execution of circulars and official instructions.

2.5. The basic functions of a school administration

The actions/functions of a school administration are:

Planning: It is the strategic management approach that takes into account both the limits and the possibilities that exist inside and outside the school unit, determining how to formulate a strategy to achieve the goals related to the school. The most fundamental of the five management functions, planning is about bridging the gap between where a school is now and where it aspires to be.

Decision making: It is necessary for the director and the association to make decisions on various issues concerning the educational unit. Decisions must be based on well-founded and appropriate information and not on mere hunches and assumptions of management. That is why it is important to thoroughly analyze all the available options and choose the best one to then implement and finally evaluate the result.

Organizing: It is a well-known saying that with better organization you achieve more. Organization refers to the division of labor, the allocation of resources, the delegation of responsibilities, and the development of relationships among teachers. The head of each school unit establishes a standard framework for linking duty and authority, which supports the effective and satisfactory fulfillment of the school's goals.

Directing /leading: Contains strategies and processes for motivating trainers, communicating with them, creating a clear vision, fostering a positive work environment, and resolving workplace conflicts.

Controlling: Necessary for the workflow of the administration, where data is analyzed, issues are regulated and the performance of employees and teachers is monitored. There are three main goals: to evaluate final results, identify any potential issues that may have occurred throughout the academic year, and determine appropriate corrective actions.

Activities such as those listed above are part of management and all work together to make the most of the school's available resources in order to meet educational goals. Every choice and action of an organization's management is scrutinized first for its economic efficiency. Its continued existence and continued profitability depend entirely on the money it generates. The economic theory states that maximizing profits is the objective of every corporate action. In recent reports profit maximization has taken on qualitative dimensions. There are also non-financial results such as the satisfaction of school members, participation in social welfare and social culture, etc. As far as the school unit is concerned, the gain is qualitative and mainly concerns successful completion of educational goals.

Students, teachers, administrators, parents, and others who serve in various positions within a school are part of a larger system regulated by a set of rules, principles, and job descriptions, accomplishing defined goals by working together and influencing each other. (Hatzipanagiotou,2003[15]). For this implementation, proper operation is required, which includes planning, coordination, institutionalization of resources (human and material), actions for the effective provision of training and human resource management. Decisions to implement the measures taken during the planning phase as well as the evaluation of the results are also necessary functions. (Saitis, 2008[16]). It is important to point out that educational units, unlike other non-profit organizations, are not exempted from the social duty to operate efficiently, to rationally handle material and immaterial assets and to continuously improve the quality of education provided. The human resource connects all actions for every private and public business and in particular the school, with the result to be at the center of the administrative process.

2.6. Evaluation of an educational management model

The Greek model of school leadership is bureaucratic, complex due to its size and structures, since the primary decisions for the design, planning and management of educational institutions are centralized. However, as Saitis (2005[17]) notes despite its stated purpose, the regional directorate in fact devolved the same authority to its region as it did to the top of the administrative pyramid. Operation and school unit is considered as the last recipient of the options for the implementation of educational policies (Andreou & Papakonstantinou, 1994[18]). There is a limited number of decisions and activities in which the teachers as well as the school unit can take part, because the coordination of cultural events and the purchase of school supplies prevails (Papanoum, 2003[19]).

The Ministry of Education is responsible for all administrative tasks and is responsible for key challenges in the management of educational human resources, such as the appointment of teachers by law and the establishment of bodies with limited authority, primarily for the execution of the decisions of the central authority (Michopoulos, 1998[20]). As a result, the central administration is able to influence the working conditions as well as the framework of the teachers in the local educational bodies and determine the method of action of the local educational bodies. As previously stated the effective use of human resources results from

effective management. In school administration, this "general" idea is arguably more critical. The successful utilization of the knowledge and skills of a school's teachers is the purpose of human resources in education.

2.7. Definition and Meaning of Human Resources (HRM)

A resource is the productive or economic factor required by the organization to carry out an activity or the means required to achieve the desired result. Human resources are special because they concern the human factor of an organization. The talent, willingness, knowledge, of all the employees of a company that contribute to the formation and execution of its purpose, vision, strategy and goals is characterized as human resources (HR) (Papalexandri & Bourandas, 2016[21]). Human resource management is concerned with the ways in which people are employed and managed by organizations. It covers the activities of strategic HRM, human capital management, knowledge management, corporate social responsibility, organizational development, resourcing (workforce planning, recruitment, selection and talent management), learning and development, performance and reward management, employee relations, employee well-being and employee service delivery. Human resource management is described as a set of actions and methods focused on the successful management of personnel at all levels of a company to achieve organizational goals (Byars & Rue, 2006[22]). Employees are the most important asset. It is appropriate and useful to treat Human Resource Management as a function that is the responsibility of all those who exercise management to a greater or lesser extent. HR managers are responsible for the implementation of effective human resource management methods.

2.8. The objectives of human resource management (HRM)

The objectives of HRM in education are:

The development and implementation of a human resources (HR) strategy that is aligned with the schools overall operational and organizational plan (HRM strategy).

The contribution of human resources for the development of a high performance culture.

Confirmation that the school has the talented, qualified and dedicated teachers it needs.

Creating a positive working relationship between the school leadership and teachers by developing a climate of mutual trust.

Encouraging the application of an ethical approach to teacher management.

2.9. Human Resources (HR) Functions

The following are mentioned as general functions:

Conducting job analyzes (determining the nature of each teacher's work).

Planning.

Orientation and training of new teachers.

Creation of incentives and benefits.

Performance evaluation.

Communication (interviewing, counseling, discipline).

Teachers training and manager development.

Building relationships and engagement with teachers.

And in addition what every school principal should know:

Health and safety of teachers.

Equal opportunity and affirmative action.

Handling complaints and internal relations.

III. METHODOLOGY

Regarding the research process, it was decided that the research will be of a quantitative nature, in order to capture the views of the teachers in the best possible way. For this purpose, a questionnaire was created which was distributed electronically to 25 secondary schools of the Prefecture of Kozani in March 2022. In total, 101 teachers answered the questionnaire.

The questionnaire is divided into nine parts. The first part describes the sample, the second part describes the teachers' statements about their trainings (more specifically, the types of trainings, the training methods, the training providers and the training methods), the third part describes the working conditions for the teachers of the sample, the fourth part describes the operation of the association and the relations between the teachers, the fifth part presents the role of the Principal (more specifically, what issues the Principal should be interested in) and the sixth part presentation of issues related to teacher evaluation. The seventh part describes teachers' statements about educational processes, the eighth part gives a summary statement about the input of training coordinators, and the ninth part describes teachers' statements about school safety and equipment.

For the questionnaire questions belonging to the five-point Likert scale ("1= Not at all", "2= A little", "3= Enough", 4= "A lot", "5= Very much"), the method applied to estimate the data is to estimate the measures of position (the mean) and dispersion (the standard deviation) of descriptive statistics. Specifically, we evaluate the questionnaire responses based on the average value as follows:

TABLE 1

Data evaluation criteria	
Average price range	Evaluation
From 1 to 1.8	Not at all
From 1.9 to 2.6	A little
From 2.7 to 3.4	Enough
From 3.5 to 4.2	A lot
From 4.3 to 5	Very much

For the rest of the questions in the questionnaire whose answers are categorical (eg, "Yes", "No"), their analysis is captured by tables of relative and cumulative (as applicable) frequencies.

The statistical package SPSS (SPSS v.20) was used for the evaluation of the data

IV. RESULTS AND FINDINGS

The Demographic characteristics of 101 people who participated in the survey.

These characteristics are gender, age and level of education. Regarding gender, men and women participate almost equally in the survey with percentages of 47.5% and 52.5% respectively. Regarding the age of the individuals, we observe a large majority of those who belong to the age group of 50-59 years (59.4%), followed by those who belong to the age group of 40-49 years (20.8%), while the cumulative frequency shows that the younger teachers under 39 make up just 6.9% of the sample. Regarding the level of education of the

teachers in the sample, it also shows that the vast majority of them have completed postgraduate studies (the cumulative frequency is 92.1%).

The teachers of the sample evaluated "University" as the most suitable (mean value = 3.77) and immediately after the Ministry of Education (mean value = 3.32). Less suitable with an average value of 2.27 were assessed the "private educational institutions".

Teachers state that they believe very much in the participation of teachers in educational activities (mean value = 4.53) and in the planning and implementation of educational activities in collaboration with other schools (mean value = 4.32). The participation of teachers in national and European Erasmus programs is also evaluated as very important for the professional development and training of teachers (mean value = 4.13).

We notice that with regard to good working conditions, the largest percentage of respondents (51.5%) state that they consider good working conditions to be very important and follow the good school environment with the same assessment (48.5%). On the other hand, participation in administrative decisions and motivation from the school Principal do not seem to be considered particularly important factors in order for the teacher to perform more at his job.

The vast majority of teachers are permanent teachers (87.1%), the majority are teachers in a General High School (57.4%), the majority have work experience between 21 and 30 years (41.6%) and 31.7% of respondents declare work experience in the same school placed at the time of the survey. To the question "Was it your first choice to become a teacher" the vast majority of respondents answered positively (78.2%).

Only the permanent teachers have completed doctoral studies. All hourly teachers have completed postgraduate studies (100%), followed by substitute teachers at a rate of 63.6% and permanent teachers at a rate of 38.6%. Only the permanent and substitute teachers have a second university degree, but less than 10%.

The teachers in our sample state that they have attended training seminars or have been retrained in administration matters (at a rate of 44.6%) and are interested in taking on higher administrative responsibilities in the future (at a rate of 36.6%).

In the question "To what extent are the following needs satisfied by your service in general and your school in particular", teachers state that all their needs (social, psychological, biological) are very satisfied with social needs first, in order of priority.

Regarding possible factors considered important in order for the teacher to perform more in his work, shows that good working conditions and good school environment are very important factors (mean value 4.36 and 4.32 respectively). Moral reward, financial reward and organizational support are declared as very important factors (mean value 4.25, 4.18 and 4.14 respectively). On the contrary, participation in administrative decisions and motivation from the school Principal are evaluated as quite important factors (mean value 3.34 and 2.98 respectively).

Teachers rate their participation in the decision-making of their educational work as very high (mean value = 3.33), they make a lot of use of the possibilities they have in their work (mean value = 3.29) and consider that the school contributes a lot to their personal development and utilization as a teacher (mean value = 3.20).

Regarding teacher evaluation criteria what consider more important, the teachers in the sample state that service consistency, good teamwork cooperation between colleagues, students, parents, and teaching ability are the most important factors. Scientific training and personality are rated as very important factors as well.

In the question of the questionnaire which concerns the evaluation of the teacher and specifically by whom it should be done. The frequency table shows that the teachers in our sample answer "Yes" to the assessment by students (58.4%), by the school principal (56.4%) and by the training coordinator (52.5%). A percentage of 41.6% states "Yes" to the evaluation by the teachers' association, while a clearly small percentage (25.7%) states "Yes" to the evaluation by the parents. Finally, it is worth mentioning that, at the same time, a non-negligible portion of teachers declares "Yes" to the absence of evaluation at a rate of 23.8%.

There are two questions about specialty courses. Specifically, the questions are whether there are the necessary classrooms and laboratories for the teaching of specialty courses and whether the school's laboratory equipment is satisfactory and modern. 74.3% of respondents answered that there are classrooms and laboratories for teaching specialty courses, but a smaller percentage of teachers (60.4%) answered that the equipment of the school's laboratories is satisfactory and modern.

The contribution of education coordinators to date in the scientific and pedagogical guidance of teachers, in supporting their educational work and in their training is assessed as sufficient.

In the overwhelming majority, teachers state that they have been trained in first aid (78.2%), while they state that they have been trained in fire safety and civil protection at a rate of 58.4% in both cases.

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In this research we saw the importance of human resource training and development for all organizations and especially for education where staff is related to the training of teachers and executives. In the modern world, training must also concern development. The training must be expanded so that individuals also develop personally. To develop those elements of their character that will help them to face changes positively, understand and adapt to changes, make better decisions, understand human behavior and introduce innovations.

The administration of a public educational organization can cooperate with the Coordinators of the educational project, with the School of Public Administration, with public educational institutions, with NGOs proposed by the Ministry of Education, with public hospitals to create educational activities. Also, the organization can create actions to exchange good practices between employees in the school itself or in neighboring schools. Finally, the School can find sponsorships (in collaboration with the school board and/or the association of parents and guardians) to organize seminars from private institutions.

The training actions aimed at staff may aim at improving individual and collective performance, teaching and crisis and conflict management, problem handling, new pedagogical methods, new technologies for their integration into daily teaching practice, cultivating interpersonal skills, dealing with changes in the working environment (children change, the school must change), work stress, mental resilience, managing diversity, multiculturalism, loss, exclusion, poverty, love as an option. Also, the educational actions may concern the understanding of teenagers, decision-making, problem analysis, communication, teamwork and cooperation, leadership, the development of oneself and others.

We have also seen that the increasing autonomy of secondary education organizations requires their ability to adapt to more competitive situations, which is achieved through internal and external quality controls of the educational services they offer. Compared to external audits, internal quality audits offered by secondary education organizations have several benefits. For example, external audit often focuses on the performance of the educational organization. It is common practice for external audit to focus on standardized indicators and parameters, with the findings used for benchmarking between educational institutions. Internal control, on the other hand, uses indicators, criteria and sub-criteria based not only on comparative assessments with other secondary education institutions, but also on assessments previously made within the institution itself. In other words, internal auditing examines results in the same way that external auditing does, but the difference between the two is that internal auditing examines management systems on a regular basis at all levels of the organization. As a result, the internal control system is more accurate and thorough than the external system. In order to assist secondary education, internal secondary resources and quality controls, this self-assessment guide has been developed. The recommendations of the self-assessment guide for the implementation of total quality management in secondary education organizations include, first and foremost, the continuous improvement of all stages of all processes as a result of regular internal reviews. In addition, leadership commitment to communication, harmonious teamwork and human resource empowerment is essential. The last point is the motivation of human resources as a consequence of their participation in the self-evaluation of the educational organization, together with their happiness with their participation and the reinforcement of the use of the results of the self-evaluation. In order to strengthen the primary teaching and learning process, all aspects that affect it

are analyzed and optimized at all levels of work and throughout the educational organization. One of these aspects is the atmosphere both inside and outside the classroom. When used in conjunction with other training services, the self-assessment guide is a component of the circular process of planning, managing and improving the primary and secondary processes provided.

In public school assessment can be done in a number of ways (none are complete and uniquely secure, but each gives clues). E.g. it can be done by discussion with the students, by discussion with the class council, it can be done by named or anonymous questionnaires, it can be done by observation from other colleagues and the administration, by external evaluators. The evaluation must start with the principal (judged by teachers, students, parents, external evaluators) and then join the teachers and the school unit.

In our research, we saw that the teachers believe that the assessment should be done by the students first and then by the school director, so it is suggested:

Extensive use of qualitative data and limited use of quantitative data.

Student participation in teacher performance evaluation.

Involvement of parents and other groups as well.

We have also found in terms of motivation that productivity goes hand in hand with the satisfaction that any organization provides to its staff. Recognizing the contribution of each employee adds significantly to the development of more loyal, skilled and effective human resources. We can reward someone if we pay them better (materially or morally), if we improve their working conditions, if we promote them, if we train them.

Due to limited resources (unfortunately instead of an increase in wages we saw a decrease), the reward can be expressed in recognition of the contribution of teachers to the teachers' association, the student community, the parents' and guardians' association (on the day of excellence awards - 26 October), by promoting them either in the local press, on the school website, on the website of the Directorate of Education, in the Municipality (remuneration) It can be expressed by creating beautiful workplaces, modern offices, with beautified spaces, air-conditioned but also rooms equipped with that it is necessary, the creation of appropriate sections of students, the distribution of tasks desired by the majority (improvement of working conditions). It can be expressed if coordinators or task force leaders are appointed (promotion), if training seminars focused on the needs of each are organized, or if they are facilitated to participate in such (training).

Steps principals should take to promote engagement include ensuring that teachers: (1) understand how they themselves contribute to the school's success, (2) understand how their efforts contribute to the school's goals, (3) that they get a sense of accomplishment from their work at school, and (4) that they are highly involved whether working alone or in groups. They should also meet periodically to discuss how to improve engagement.

We also found that when a school has students with interests either in the Pan-Hellenic exams, or in extracurricular activities (participation in student competitions in physics, chemistry, biology, mathematics, IT, poetry, short story, theater, student virtual business, rhetorical competitions, technology, robotics, photography, participation in activities related to mental resilience, environmental programs, health education programs, professional guidance, etc.). This should be a motivation for teachers.

In this paper, an integrated political management of the human resources of secondary education was presented and analyzed, which underlined the importance of an integrated political management of the human resources of secondary education in Greece. At the same time, several flaws in current practice were identified and recommendations were made for the current level of improvement. It must be emphasized that a "symptomatic treatment" will not lead to long-term changes and improvements. The creation and implementation of an integrated human resource management system for education is the only method that the system can "deliver" to its students and avoid the effects of anachronistic ways of human resource management in secondary education. Otherwise, a management philosophy that is considered "outdated" will continue to be used, in which management attempts to "respond" when issues and omissions arise. Because of this behavior, it is impossible to deliver public education that meets the real demands of society and teachers.

VI. Research limitations

The present research is exploratory in nature and is based on quantitative analysis of primary data collected from a relatively small sample of respondents, which makes it difficult to generalize the results.

VII. Implications

The purpose of this research was to evaluate the role of the HR function in the management of human resources in secondary education. The findings support that good working conditions and a good school environment are very important factors as well as the interactive relationship between students and teachers in terms of performance. HR managers need to be aware of the teacher needs in Greek schools. Utilizing the abilities, knowledge and skills of teachers should be a strategic objective. The chronic problems of education demonstrate the necessity for research that can contribute to prevention, responsibility and self-commitment.

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